

IN MEMORIAM
Dr Dubravka Regner
(1944-2025)

Dr Dubravka Regner, marine biologist and retired Scientific Advisor, was born in Zagreb, Yugoslavia, in 1944. She graduated in Biology from the University of Belgrade, Faculty of Natural Sciences, in 1967, and went on to earn her MSc (1970) and PhD (1980) degrees from the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Natural Sciences.

Dr Regner dedicated her professional life to the study of the Adriatic Sea. She was working at the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries in Split from 1968 to 1994, and later at the Institute of Marine Biology in Kotor from 1994 until her retirement in 2008.

Her scientific work focused on the biodiversity and ecology of zooplankton, with particular emphasis on copepods, the dominant meso-zooplankton group. She made significant contributions to understanding the horizontal distribution of plankton across the Adriatic Sea – from coastal zones to the open sea and from the northern to the southern basin. Her research encompassed seasonal and long-term fluctuations in plankton density and biomass, species frequency and dominance, diversity indices, and relationships with environmental parameters. She also studied the ecological consequences of eutrophication and played a pioneering role in seawater quality monitoring along Montenegrin beaches.

Dr Regner enriched her expertise through international scientific visits and training in France, Italy, and Greece. She was an active member of several scientific organizations, including the Main Council of the Yugoslav Society for Water Protection, UNEP, and CIESM. Throughout her distinguished career, she published more than 150 scientific papers and environmental studies, leaving a lasting impact on marine biology in the Adriatic region.

On 15 September 2025, we received the sad news of her passing. Dr. Dubravka Regner will be remembered with great respect as a dedicated and inquisitive scientist and a warm person.

May her soul rest in peace.

Institute of Marine Biology, University of Montenegro